

FILIPINO READING COMPREHENSION LEVEL OF GRADE 3 LEARNERS: BASIS FOR READING INTERVENTION PLAN

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ABSTRACT

The ability of a reader to comprehend and analyze written texts is measured by their reading comprehension level. It is divided into three levels: analytical, inferential, and literal. The reader must use a different set of abilities and techniques for each level. It is an essential ability for both lifetime learning and academic success. The purpose of this study is to seek the reading comprehension level of Filipino Grade 3 learners using the three levels of comprehension questions: *analysis/pagsusuri*, *inferential/paghinuha*, and *literal/literal*. The three levels of comprehension questions were utilized to determine the learners' level using a convenience sampling method. The method is often used when the researcher is unable to access a random or representative sample due to time, budget, or logistic constraints. The data collected indicated that, with a score of 77.78%, the learners' comprehension level in literal questions is at the instructional level. With a score of 33.33%, the learners' comprehension level for inferential questions was frustration. Furthermore, with a score of 33.33% on analysis questions, the learners' comprehension level was frustration. With a mean score of 48.15, it was further determined that Filipino Grade 3 learners' overall reading comprehension level is frustration.

Keywords: *Comprehension Level; Academic Success; Literal; Inferential; Analytical*

INTRODUCTION

Reading comprehension is the process of making meaning from text. The goal, therefore, is to gain an overall understanding of what is described in the text rather than to obtain meaning

from isolated words or sentences. In understanding read text information, children develop mental models, or representations of the meaning of the text ideas during the reading process (Wooley, 2011). It is a skill that is critical to the educational success of all individuals. Without adequate reading comprehension, students can struggle in many subject areas. Reading comprehension is an important skill needed for all areas of school (Baier, 2005).

Reading comprehension is a complex interaction among automatic and strategic cognitive processes that enables the reader to create a mental representation of the text (Van den Broek & Espin, 2012). Comprehension depends not only on the characteristics of the reader, such as prior knowledge and working memory, but also on language processes, such as basic reading skills, decoding, vocabulary, sensitivity to text structure, inference, and motivation. Comprehension also requires effective use of strategic processes, such as metacognition and comprehension monitoring. As readers mature in their comprehension skills, they can progress efficiently from the stage of learning to read to the ultimate goal of reading to learn (Yovanoff, Duesbery, Alonzo, & Tindal, 2005).

Pardo (2004) elucidated that the process of comprehension begins before we start to 'read' and continues even after the 'reading' is finished. Good readers use pre-reading strategies like previewing the text and post-reading strategies like summarizing in addition to the many strategies they use to make meaning during 'reading' itself. By dividing instruction into pre-reading, during-reading, and post-reading, teachers can design activities for each stage that will improve student's comprehension and also provide opportunities for teachers to demonstrate strategies that readers can use at each stage.

However, reading, specifically comprehension, has been seen as a perennial problem in literacy. In Ambacan Elementary School, specifically in Grade 3, the learners' performance in subject areas is affected by their reading ability as seen in the results of their quizzes and tests. Based on initial observations during reading classes, learners have difficulty answering questions posed after reading the texts.

This problem provoked the researcher, the class adviser, to investigate Grade 3 learners' reading comprehension levels and eventually design an intervention plan to improve the reading comprehension level of the learners.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the level of reading comprehension skills of Grade 3 learners in Ambacan Elementary School as the basis for designing a reading intervention plan. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

A. What is the reading comprehension level of Grade 3 learners in terms of:

1. Literal/*Literal* questions;
2. Inferential/*Paghinuha* questions; and
3. Analysis/*Pagsusuri* questions?

B. What reading intervention plan can be designed to improve the reading comprehension of Grades 3 learners?

METHODOLOGY

This research utilized the descriptive design. It aimed to describe the reading comprehension level of Grade 3 learners. Specifically, it investigated the learners' level in the three levels of comprehension questions: literal, inferential, and analysis.

a. Sampling

The study employed the descriptive case design using the convenience sampling method. Convenience sampling is a type of non-probability sampling method that relies on data collection from the population members who are conveniently available to participate in the study. The method is often used when the researcher is unable to access a random or representative sample due to time, budget, or logistical constraints.

In this study, the researcher used a convenience sampling method to conduct a study on the reading comprehension level of Grade 3 learners in terms of literal, inferential, and analysis questions.

b. Data Collection

For the gathering of data, I followed the necessary protocols for the conduct of a research study. First, I submitted a letter to the school head of Ambacan Elementary School asking for full consent for the conduct of the study. After securing the necessary permission from my school head, I sent letters to the parents of my learners asking for their consent to the inclusion of their children in the study.

The data used in this research were taken through testing using the Phil-IRI Pretest. The test was administered in the first quarter of the month specifically in September 2022. After the assessment, the researcher consolidated the results of the Phil-IRI test and recorded the data for analysis.

RESULTS

This research utilized the Phil-IRI Pretest in Filipino, specifically Pretest Set D to assess the reading comprehension level of Grade 3 learners. Table 1 shows the Reading Comprehension Level of the Grade 3 learners. The results showed that the learner participants got the highest percentage score in literal questions. Based on the Phil-IRI Oral Reading Profile, the learners' comprehension level of literal questions is Instructional. This means that the Grade 3 learners are more likely to answer approximately 77.78% of the literal questions without the teacher's guidance. This further implies that they are proficient in answering questions in which the answers are explicitly stated in the text.

In terms of the learners' comprehension level of inferential questions, the assessment showed that their level is Frustration. This connotes that, if asked inferential questions from the text they have read, they are more likely to get 33.33% correct answers. This also means that Grade 3 learners can answer questions in which answers are implied by the text with the guidance of the teacher.

Moreover, it can be manifested in the Phil-IRI result that the learners' comprehension level in analysis questions is at the Frustration Level. This means that, if given questions that pertain to using evidence in the text to come up with an answer, the learners are more likely to get approximately 33.33% correct answers only. This also means that they find difficulty answering high-order thinking questions.

Table 1. Reading Comprehension Level of Grade 3
Three Levels of Comprehension Questions

Comprehension Question	Percentage Score	Level
Literal/Literal	77.78%	Instructional
Inferential/Paghinuha	33.33%	Frustration
Analysis/Pagsusuri	33.33%	Frustration

To get the overall reading comprehension level of Grade 3 learners, the researcher took the mean score and percentage of the 9 learners in the six comprehension questions.

Table 2. Overall reading Comprehension Level of Grade 3

Mean Score	Percentage	Reading Comprehension Level
2.89	48.17%	Frustration

Based on Table 2, it can be gleaned that Grade 3 learners' overall reading comprehension level is Frustration. If asked questions from the text, the respondents are more likely to get 48.17% correct answers only. This means that they are not reading at their expected level or the Grade 3 level and they need immediate intervention.

DISCUSSION

These results imply that the teacher should be aware of the different types of questions that can assess different levels of reading comprehension of the learners, and use a variety of questions to challenge and support their learners' reading development. Teachers should also provide appropriate intervention plans and resources to develop learners' reading comprehension levels in terms of literal, inferential, and analysis questions. By doing so, the teacher can help their learners improve their reading comprehension skills and achieve academic success.

The results also suggest that reading intervention strategies can help improve the reading skills of learners who are struggling with reading comprehension. Reading intervention strategies are interventions put into place to help learners who have difficulties in decoding words, poor comprehension skills, and low reading fluency. The results also indicate that different types of reading interventions may be more effective for different learners, depending on their specific

needs and strengths. Therefore, the proposed reading intervention plan should be based on a data-based which involves identifying the learners' reading comprehension problems, selecting appropriate interventions, implementing them with fidelity, and monitoring their progress. The goal of the reading intervention plan is to help the learners achieve reading comprehension levels in terms of literal, inferential, and analytical. By using effective reading intervention strategies, teachers can help these learners overcome their reading challenges and enjoy the benefits of reading.

The intervention plan is designed for students who need to improve their reading comprehension skills in different types of questions the plan is composed of objectives, strategies, assessments, time frames, and performance indicators.

Reading Intervention Plan

Objectives	Strategies	Assessment	Time Frame	Performance Indicator
To improve the learners' reading comprehension level in terms of literal, inferential, and analysis based on the text they read.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Pre-teach vocabulary and background knowledge that are relevant to the text. ● Use graphic organizers to help students organize the main ideas and details of the text. ● Model and teach different types of questions and how to answer them using evidence from the text. ● Provide guided practice and feedback on answering literal, inferential, and analysis questions. ● Use cooperative learning strategies to 	quizzes, tests, and oral reports based on the texts read written responses, projects, and presentations based on the texts essays, debates, and portfolios based on the texts read	November 2022 to May 2023	Learner will <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● increase their accuracy and fluency in answering literal, inferential, and analysis questions from pre-test to post-test ● demonstrate their understanding of the text by writing a summary or a response that includes the main idea, supporting details, and personal connections or opinions ● to show improvement in their reading comprehension skills on standardized tests or curriculum-

	<p>encourage peer discussion and collaboration in answering questions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Monitor and assess students' progress and adjust instruction accordingly. 			based measures.
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Conclusions

This study was made to determine the reading comprehension level Filipino of Grade 3 learners in Ambacan Elementary Schools. The assessment of the learners' reading comprehension level investigated the learners' ability in the three types of comprehension questions namely literal/literal, inferential/pagina, and analysis/pagsusuri.

After the collection and analysis of data, it was found that the learners' comprehension of literal questions is at the Instructional level since it gained a percentage score of 77.78%, while their level in inferential questions is at the Frustration level with a 33.33% score. Moreover, the learners' comprehension level in analysis questions is at a Frustration level since they garnered an overall percentage score of 33.33%.

With the aforementioned data, it can be concluded that the learners can answer literal questions correctly without any assistance from the teacher, while they can answer inferential questions with the assistance of the teacher. On the other hand, the results show that the learners have difficulty answering analysis questions.

The study also discovered that the overall reading comprehension level in Filipino Grade 3 learners is at a Frustration level since they gained an overall percentage score of 48.17%. Thus, it can be concluded that the learners' reading comprehension level in Filipino is below their expected standard.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made.

1. A reading intervention plan will be made giving weight to developing the learners' ability to answer inferential questions and analysis questions. Part of the intervention should be focused on the enrichment of the learners' ability to answer literal questions.
2. A follow-up research to test the effectiveness of the intervention plan shall be made.
3. Regular monitoring of the learners' reading progress shall be done to ensure proper implementation of the reading program and activities.

4. Other researchers should conduct the same study in their schools to find out the reading status of their learners and eventually craft an intervention program out of it.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In social studies, this set of principles should always be taken into consideration to protect the rights of the participants, ensure the validity of results, and maintain integrity (Scribbr, n.d.). The participants are reminded that they have the right to refuse to participate and that participation is voluntary if they choose to do so, and/or remain anonymous. This is in line with the principle of protecting the participant's identity. Lastly, in the informed consent, the participants would be briefed about the potential risks and benefits.

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